

ZENODO COMMUNITY USER MANUAL

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Image on title page by Mael Balland on Unsplash

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FOODCLIC COMMUNITY URLS

Collection URL

<https://zenodo.org/communities/foodclic/>

Links directly to our community collection.

URL for uploading FoodCLIC outputs

<https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=foodclic>

HISTORY OF CHANGE

Version N°	Date	Pages changed	Changes
1	16/4/2023	-	-
2	05/01/2026	All document (particularly chapter 3)	General update of the guide, considering Zenodo's update and new features

1. INTRODUCTION

This document provides guidance on how to implement the Data Management Plan concerning sharing the data generated throughout the FoodCLIC project. It includes a step-by-step guide on how to deposit finalized and ready-to-share files, as well as guidelines about data format good practices.

Below, the why, where, when, what, and who are summarized, describing the guidelines defined by the European Commission for any Horizon Europe project.

1.1 WHY?

Proper Research Data Management is mandatory for any Horizon Europe project generating or reusing research data. It is a key part of Horizon Europe's open science requirements.

In Horizon Europe, beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles, and should at least do the following:

- Prepare a **Data Management Plan (DMP)** and keep it updated throughout the course of the project
- Deposit data in a **trusted repository** and provide open access to it ('as open as possible, as closed as necessary').
- Provide information (via the same repository) about any **research output or any other tools** and instruments that may be needed to **re-use or validate the data** (e.g. [data dictionary](#) for each dataset deposited)

1.2 WHERE?

Trusted repositories are infrastructures that provide reliable and long-term access to digital resources such as data, publications, etc.

Within the FoodCLIC project, as laid out in the Data Management Plan (**Deliverable 1.2** - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535493>), we opted for depositing the generated data (ensuring full respect of the GDPR) in Zenodo, a general-purpose repository, initially created to support research commissioned by the EU, that presents the essential characteristics of trusted repositories (e.g., security provisions, services for the creation of machine actionable metadata, long-term preservation of data, etc.).

We created a Zenodo community to aggregate (and easily share) all FoodCLIC-related data and documents. The FoodCLIC community can be accessed using this [link](#).

1.3 WHEN?

In Horizon Europe, data should be deposited as soon as possible after its generation and, at the latest, by the end of the project (with or without embargo conditions, as most appropriate).

There are, however, some additional requirements:

- Data underpinning a scientific publication should be deposited **at the latest at the time of publication**, and in line with **standard community practices**.
- In cases of **public emergency**, if requested by the granting authority, **immediate open access should be provided**. If exceptions to open access to data apply, data should be made available at least to the legal entities that need the data to address the public emergency.
- In **exceptional cases**, data can be deposited after the project has finished.

1.4 WHAT?

'AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE, AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY'

In Horizon Europe, research data should be made open access by default and licensed under the latest version of CC BY (attribution required) or CC 0 (public domain), or equivalent.

It is recognized that data should be 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary', and exceptions can be made when providing open access to data. In FoodCLIC's Data Management Plan, exceptions for open access have been foreseen for sensitive or confidential information that may be generated. These include personal data that cannot be anonymized or when consent for sharing individual data was not provided.

Horizon Europe requires that, at the time of depositing research data in a trusted repository, one must also provide access (via the repository) to information about any research output, or any other tools or instruments that may be needed to re-use or validate the research data.

- "Research outputs, tools, and instruments" may include data, software, algorithms, protocols, models, workflows, electronic notebooks, and others.
- What type of information should be provided? A **detailed description** of the research output/tool/instrument, how to access it, any dependencies on commercial products (e.g. software), potential version/type, potential parameters, etc.

Besides information about these outputs, beneficiaries are encouraged to provide **open (digital) access** to the research outputs, tools, and instruments themselves unless legitimate interests or constraints apply.

This information should be stated in the Description field (in the second section of the form, when uploading the output at Zenodo).

In general, the types of data that should/can be deposited in Zenodo are included in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 1. Types of data generated within the FoodCLIC project.

PREPARATION	GENERATED DATA	SUPPORTING ANALYSIS	REPORTING AND DISSEMINATION
Protocols Plans/guides Informed consent form Ethics committee docs	Datasets Videos Audios Photos Text Geospatial Scripts	Scripts Syntax Qualitative coding system files	Reports (deliverables) Presentations Policy briefs Flyers Videos Audios (interviews or presentations) Scientific publications Posters Software

1.5 WHO?

When a task or project is considered finished, the lead authors/partners should prepare the files aggregating and harmonizing all relevant (anonymized) generated data within their task/project to upload into the Zenodo Community. At that point, lead partners should confirm with the participating partners that the data they have provided is acceptable to be openly shared or if other access levels would be needed.

When necessary, the Ethics Advisory Board should be contacted to clarify any ethics concerns that may arise.

After creating the data files in the preferred formats, the partner responsible (frequently, the task leaders or lead authors of the output) should upload them on the Zenodo FoodCLIC Community following the step-by-step described in section 3.

Specifically, regarding deliverables, they should be uploaded in the Zenodo FoodCLIC Community after being submitted to the EU portal by the project management. The upload of relevant data for validating the findings reported in deliverables is of the responsibility of the lead authors.

Table 2 summarizes the different responsibilities depending on the type of data.

Table 2. Attributed responsibilities for uploading data in the Zenodo FoodCLIC Community.

FILE TYPE	RESPONSIBILITY FOR UPLOADING
Deliverables	Project management
Other output documents (scientific papers, posters, etc.)	Lead authors
Data used in outputs (files that may be needed to validate/recheck findings)	Lead authors of the output (e.g., deliverables; scientific papers)

2. DATA FORMAT

Different types of data are acquired, processed, and stored (preserved and/or archived) in different ways and file formats. Many proprietary file formats are “containers” for standard file formats. By packaging them into these containers, a software and/or hardware developer can provide additional functionality, usually by streamlining a process, to analyse data acquired on their platform. However, this has the negative consequence of making these data less interoperable.

File formats can be either lossless or lossy: that is, whether data is uncompressed (such as TIFF for images) or compressed (such as JPEG for images) to remove redundant information and thus reduce file size. It is common practice to do analyses on lossy data, but this does not necessarily mean that these data should be the ones that should be kept for long-term storage. In this context, it is highly likely that the most important file to consider for long-term storage through its curation lifecycle is either the first file (the one that was initially captured) or a direct lossless standard file format version from this one.

The key consideration to make centres on longevity and interoperability and to be as much FAIR as possible – proprietary versus standard formats. There is no guarantee that existing proprietary file formats will exist in the future. For example, many Microsoft file formats such as Word and Excel may be in common use now, but this does not deny the possibility that they will become obsolete in the future. Software and file format obsolescence will be even more pronounced for bespoke file formats that were created as part of an individual project.

To guide the FoodCLIC partners in choosing which file formats to choose for the different types of data, we laid out in Table 3 the preferred and non-preferred formats as recommended by the [DANS - Data Archiving and Networked Services](#). Preferred formats are file formats of which DANS – based on international agreements – is confident that will offer the best long-term guarantees in terms of usability, accessibility, and sustainability. Non-preferred formats are file formats that are widely used in addition to the preferred formats, and that will be moderately to reasonably usable, accessible, and robust in the long term. It may be an option to make certain original data available in ‘non-preferred format(s)’, such as in the case of current usage formats. In these cases, one should deposit the data in these original formats as well as in preferred formats aimed at long-term sustainability.

In Table 3, hyperlinks to the description of each type of data and file formats are provided, as guidance.

Table 3. Recommended file formats to be uploaded for long-term storage.

TYPE OF DATA	PREFERRED FORMAT(S)	NON-PREFERRED FORMAT(S)
Text documents	PDF/A (.pdf) ODT (.odt)	Microsoft Word (.doc) Office Open XML (.docx) Rich Text File (.rtf) PDF other than PDF/A (.pdf)
Plain text	Unicode text (.txt)	Non-Unicode text (.txt)
Markup language	XML (.xml) HTML (.html) Related files: .css , .xslt , .js , .es	SGML (.sgml) Markdown (.md)
Programming languages	MATLAB NetCDF Text-Fabric	
Spreadsheets	ODS (.ods) CSV (.csv)	Microsoft Excel (.xls) Office Open XML Workbook (.xlsx) PDF/A (.pdf)
Databases	SQL (.sql) SIARD (.siard) CSV (.csv)	Microsoft Access (.mdb, .accdb) dBase (.dbf) HDF5 (.hdf5, .he5, .h5)
Statistical data	SPSS (.dat/.sps)	SPSS Portable (.por)

TYPE OF DATA	PREFERRED FORMAT(S)	NON-PREFERRED FORMAT(S)
	STATA (.dat/.DO) R	SPSS (.sav) STATA (.dta) SAS (.7dat; .sd2; .tpt)
Raster images	JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg) TIFF (.tif, .tiff) PNG (.png) JPEG 2000 (.jp2) DICOM (.dcm)	
Vector images	SVG (.svg)	Adobe Illustrator (.ai) EPS (.eps) WMF/EMF (.wmf, .emf) CDR (.cdr)
Audio	BWF (.bwf) MXF (.mxf) Matroska (.mka) FLAC (.flac) OPUS	WAVE (.wav) MP3 (.mp3) AAC (.aac, .m4a) AIFF (.aif, .aiff) OGG (.ogg)
Video	MXF (.mxf) Matroska (.mkv)	MPEG-4 (.mp4, .m4a, .m4v, ...) MPEG-2 (.mpg, .mpeg, .m2v, .mpg2, ...) AVI QuickTime (.mov, .qt)

TYPE OF DATA	PREFERRED FORMAT(S)	NON-PREFERRED FORMAT(S)
Computer Aided Design (CAD)	AutoCAD DXF version R12 (ASCII) (.dxf) SVG (.svg)	Autocad DXF, version different than R12 (ASCII) (.dxf) DWG (.dwg) DGN (.dgn)
Geographical Information Systems (GIS)	GML (.gml) MIF/MID (.mif/.mid) GeoJSON (.json)	Esri Shapefiles (.shp & related files) MapInfo (.tab & related files) KML (.kml, .kmz) Esri Geodatabase (.gdb) Project files / Workspaces (.mxd, .wor, .qgs)
Georeferenced images	GeoTIFF (.tif, .tiff)	TIFF World File (.tfw & .tif, possibly with additional files) JPEG World File (.jgw & .jpg, possibly with additional files) ERDAS IMAGINE File Format (.img)
Raster GIS	ASCII GRID (.asc, .txt)	Esri GRID (.grd & bijbehorende bestanden) Surfer Grid (.grd; .srf) ERDAS IMAGINE File Format (.img)
3D	WaveFront Object (.obj) Polygon file format (.ply)	Autodesk FBX (.fbx) Blender (.blend)

TYPE OF DATA	PREFERRED FORMAT(S)	NON-PREFERRED FORMAT(S)
	X3D (.x3d) COLLADA (.dae)	3D PDF (.pdf)
RDF	RDF/XML (.rdf) Trig (.trig) Turtle (.ttl) NTriples (.nt) JSON-LD	
Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis (CAQDAS)	REFI-QDA (Qualitative Data Analysis)	ATLAS.TI copy bundle NVivo project file

3. SUBMITTING OUTPUTS TO THE ZENODO FOODCLIC COMMUNITY

1. Access the upload URL: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=foodclic>
2. Log in into the Zenodo account using email, GitHub, ORCID, or OpenAIRE account.

If one do not have a Zenodo account, create one by selecting the Sign Up option.

The sign-up form includes the following elements:

- Buttons for "Sign up with GitHub", "Sign up with ORCID", and "Sign up with OpenAIRE".
- A separator "— OR —".
- Input fields for "Username", "Full name", "Affiliations", "Email Address" (with a note "Please use an institutional email address"), and "Password".
- A "Sign up" button at the bottom.

The login form includes the following elements:

- Buttons for "Sign in with ORCID", "Sign in with GitHub", and "Sign in with OpenAIRE".
- A separator "OR".
- Input fields for "Email Address" and "Password".
- A "Log in" button.
- Links for "New to Zenodo? Sign up" and "Privacy notice" at the bottom.

3. Confirm that the submission is being performed into the FoodCLIC community (top of your screen)

4. Drag and drop the files to upload or choose the files saved on one's IT interface
The dataset (group of files to be uploaded together) should be under 50GB and up to 100 files by upload. If wanting to upload many files (>20), it might be preferable to bundle them (e.g. ZIP). If the dataset exceeds this limit, please contact the ULisboa-FM team.

The upload interface includes the following elements:

- A "Files" dropdown menu.
- Storage availability indicators: "0 out of 100 files" and "0 bytes out of 50.00 GB".
- A dashed box containing the text "Drag and drop files" and an "Upload files" button.
- A warning message: "File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload."

- Fill in the “**Basic Informations**” section, where there are the **only mandatory fields** for submitting into Zenodo: Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Resource Type, Title, and Creators. Additionally, fill in the appropriate license.
Nevertheless, it is advisable to fill in the maximum and most complete as possible information about the file you are uploading, since it improves findability and reusability

The screenshot shows the Zenodo upload interface. On the left, the 'Basic information' section includes fields for 'Digital Object Identifier' (with a 'Do you already have a DOI for this upload?' question), 'Resource type', 'Title', 'Publication date', and 'Creators'. On the right, the 'Description' section features a rich text editor with a toolbar and a 'Licenses' dropdown menu currently set to 'Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International'. A copyright statement is visible at the bottom of the description area.

Notes:

- **Digital Object Identifier (DOI):** if one do not have a DOI, choose “No, I need one”, and Zenodo generates one for the output. If that document was already published, then, add its respective DOI;
- **Publication date:** if the document has already been published, please, state the date of first publication (e.g., project deliverables should use the date of submission in the EU platform).
- **Description:** adequately describe the document so it is easy for someone not familiar with the FoodCLIC project to understand the content of the files and what it was used for, increasing the chances of data re-use. A detailed description of the research output/tool/instrument, how to access it, any dependencies on commercial products (e.g., software), potential version/type, potential parameters, etc., should be stated here. If it is a published work, use the abstract or executive summary.
- **License:** By default, CC-BY 4.0 (attribution required) is the one indicated, but it depends on the resource type.

OPTIONAL SECTIONS (though recommended to fill in!)

- Recommended Information** is important to further describe the file you are uploading, being possible to give information about other contributors apart from the authors, keywords, language, timeline of the file construction, version, and publisher.

Recommended information ▼

Contributors

+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects

Search for a subject by name ▼

Languages

Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish") ▼

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

Dates

+ Add date

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher

Zenodo

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

Notes:

- **Publisher:** if the document has already been published, replace “Zenodo” (which appears by default) by the journal/site where it has been published.
2. On the **Funding** section, add the FoodCLIC European Commission grant number/code if that is the case. If not, add other specific grant codes.

Funding ▼

Awards/Grants

+ Add

+ Add custom

FOODCLIC — integrated urban FOOD policies – developing sustainability Co-benefits, spatial Linkages, social Inclusion and sectoral Connections to transform food systems in city-regions 101060717

European Commission

3. On the **Alternate Identifiers** section, if the work is published elsewhere (e.g., in a book, on a website), relate it with the identifier from that site (e.g., URL, ISBN, etc.)

Alternate identifiers

Alternate identifiers

+ Add identifier

- On the **Related works** section, identify if the file is related in some way with other output (e.g., supplement, continuation)

Related works

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

+ Add related work

- On the **References** section, insert the work's references. Remember that those sections are optional to fill in

References

References

+ Add reference

- When uploading a **Software**, this section can be used to describe where to find it (repository), its programming language, and its status (e.g., in progress, active, inactive, etc.)

Software

🔗 Repository URL

URL or link where the code repository is hosted.

🔗 Programming language

Repository's programming language.

💡 Development Status

Repository current status.

7. The next sections (**Published Information** and **Conference**) are useful for already published works or presented in conferences.

Publishing information

Journal

Title
Title of the journal in which the article was published

ISSN
International Standard Serial Number

Volume
e.g. 645

Issue
e.g. 7

Page range or article number
e.g. 15-23 or A29

Imprint (Book, Report, or Conference proceedings)

Book, report, or proceedings title
Title of the book, report, or proceedings which this upload is part of

ISBN
International Standard Book Number

Place
Place where the book or report was published

Pagination
e.g. 15-23 or 158

Edition
The edition of the book

Thesis

Awarding university

Awarding department

Thesis type
The type of thesis (e.g. Masters, PhD, Engineers, Bachelors)

Submission date
Submission date in YYYY-MM-DD format.

Defense date
Defense date in YYYY-MM-DD format.

Conference

Title

Acronym

Place
Location where the conference took place.

Dates
e.g. 21-22 November 20

Session
Session within the conference.

Part
Part within the session.

Website

8. In the last optional section (**Domain specific fields**), one can add other fields, from a vast menu, to better characterize the output.

Domain specific fields

9. To conclude the upload, it should be submitted for reviewing. Only after being revised by the community's curators, will it be visible and/or accessible by everybody. Before submitting, one can use the Preview option. Also, the information already registered in the platform can be saved at any time as a draft before submitting.

Draft ⓘ

📁 Save draft

👁️ Preview

📤 Submit for review

🔗 Share

Notes:

- To being able to manage drafts, click on the My dashboard tab (top bar of your screen); there, it is possible to find all saved documents and respective information (as well as already submitted outputs).
 - After published, it is still possible to modify the metadata of the outputs (e.g., description, title, keywords, etc.); but it is not possible, at that stage, to modify the submitted output. To alter it, one has to create another version of the same output.
10. To conclude the upload, it is possible to decide about its visibility. Considering the EU sharing data policy, outputs should be as Public as possible, allowing everybody to see them. However, Zenodo enables to restrict accessibility without term or just for a period of time (play an embargo).

Visibility *

Files only

Public

Restricted

Public

The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo ⓘ
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Notes:

- Embargos are foreseen in the Data Management Plan due to constraints in the time-to-publish results through scientific publications, theses, or dissertations. The embargo period will be as long as strictly necessary for the mentioned purposes, not exceeding 1.5 years after the project ends.
 - For datasets upload, we advise the embargo of data for 1 year after the project ends.
- Even when restricting the output's access, the metadata of the output is always public.

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